

1 **OCEANOGRAPHICAL PATTERNS DURING A SUMMER UPWELLING-**
2 **DOWNWELLING EVENT IN THE NORTHERN GALICIAN RIAS. COMPARISON**
3 **WITH THE WHOLE RIA SYSTEM (NW of Iberian Peninsula)**
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22 **Abstract.** Summer upwelling and downwelling processes were characterized in
23 the Northern Galician Rias during July and August 2008 by means of sampling
24 carried out onboard R/V *Mytilus* (CSIC) and R/V *Lura* (IEO). Thermohaline
25 variables, dissolved oxygen, nutrients, chlorophyll, phytoplankton, ciliates and
26 zooplankton abundances were measured at sections located in the Rias of Viveiro,
27 Barqueiro and Ortigueira and their adjacent shelves. Ekman transport was
28 calculated from *QuikSCAT* satellite, upwelling intensity estimated with upwelling
29 index from the average daily geostrophic winds, and SST maps obtained from
30 NASA GHRSSST satellite. Ekman transport and SST behaviour showed two
31 different patterns: (i) offshore and upwelling favourable conditions on 13-22nd of
32 July; (ii) onshore and downwelling favourable conditions from 23rd July to 19th
33 August). During upwelling, TS diagram showed an intrusion of Eastern North
34 Atlantic Central Water affecting the continental shelf but not the rias. Nutrient salt
35 concentrations increased with depth, reaching their maximum values near the
36 mouth of Ortigueira Ria. During downwelling, coastal water increased its
37 temperature (18.5-19.8°C) and was retained inside rias; nutrients were nearly
38 depleted, except for the innermost ria (estuarine zone) due to fluvial nutrient
39 inputs. In this inner area, the maximum of chlorophyll-*a* (Barqueiro Ria) was
40 observed. Low phytoplankton abundances were measured in both cases, even
41 though a short increase in the plankton biomass was observed inside rias during
42 upwelling, while under downwelling a small red tide of *Lingulodinium polyedrum*
43 was detected. During the upwelling period Northern Rias tend to be mesotrophic
44 systems as revealed by nutrient concentrations, chlorophyll levels and plankton
45 abundances. On the contrary, in similar situations, the Western Rias behaves as
46 eutrophics.
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48 In the Northern Galician shelf, the average of upwelling (downwelling) was 1.9±0.8
49 (2.1±1.0) events·yr⁻¹ from May to September (1990-2008) considering at least one
50 week with favourable wind conditions and UI averages out of the range of ±500
51 m³·s⁻¹·km⁻¹.
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Keywords: thermohaline variables; nutrient salts; chlorophyll; plankton; ciliates; Galician rias .

1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal upwelling is one of the main factors controlling the circulation in the upper layers of the ocean waters (Fraga, 1981). During upwelling events, colder and saltier waters from deeper layers, inject nutrients into the illuminated surface layers, favouring phytoplankton growth (Wooster and Reid, 1963). Due to the high productivity of these world regions they are profusely researched (Cushing, 1969). This is the case of the Current System of California (Bograd et al, 2009; Hickey and Royer, 2008), Peru-Humboldt (Silva et al. 2009; Karstensen and Ulloa, 2008), Canaries (Barton, 2008; Pastor et al. 2008) and Benguela (Burls and Reason, 2008; Shannon, 2009). In the North Atlantic Ocean, the Eastern North Atlantic Upwelling System extends from the south of Dakar at 10°N to the tip of the Iberian Peninsula at 44°N (Wooster et al., 1976). Its upper boundary is in the Galician coast where upwelling of Eastern North Atlantic Central Water (ENACW), located between 70-500 m depth, usually occurs during spring and summer (Fraga, 1981; Rios et al., 1992). ENACW upwelling intensifies between the Cape Finisterre and Punta Rocundo (42° 52' -43°17'N) and high concentrations of nitrate can be detected along the upwelling core in the Western Rias coast (Fraga, 1981; Prego et al., 1999a). Galicia which is situated in the north-western corner of the Iberian Peninsula, has three different littoral orientations. This fact makes the effect of northerly prevailing wind conditions (Torres et al., 2003; Alvarez et al., 2005a; Gómez-Gesteira et al., 2006) on upwelling development to be different both in probability and intensity at north of Cape Ortegal, where are the Northern Rias, between Capes Ortegal and Finisterre, where are the Middle Rias, and south of Cape Finisterre, where are the Western Rias (Figure 1).

Upwelling events in the Western Rias have been intensively studied from hydrographical (Fraga, 1981; Alvarez-Salgado et al., 1993; Prego et al., 2001; Herrera et al., 2008) and biogeochemical (Tenore et al., 1982; Blanton et al., 1984; Prego et al., 1995; Alvarez-Salgado et al., 1996; Bernárdez et al., 2006) points of view. The relationship between upwelling and thermohaline variables has been studied extensively in the western Galician coast (Nogueira et al., 1997; Pardo, 2001; Torres, 2003; Dale et al., 2004; Alvarez et al., 2005b) because the emergence of low temperature and high salinity in the surface and subsurface waters (Hu et al., 2001) is a good indicator of upwelling. In contrast with upwelling events south of Finisterre which are more intense and closer to the coast, upwelling events in the Northern Rias is discontinuous and remains mainly near the edge of the continental shelf (Prego and Bao, 1997). Upwelling in the Middle Rias of Artabro Gulf, is characterized by the no entrance of ENACW into the rias, while the opposite occurs in the Western Rias where ENACW upwells inside them (Prego and Varela, 1998).

In contrast with the Western Galician Rias, Northern Galician Rias has been scarcely investigated existing some researches focused on biological (Sánchez et al., 1998) and sedimentary aspects (Otero et al., 2000; Lorenzo, 2007). Upwelling-downwelling studies have not been extensively undertaken in this northern Galician zone, excepting some recent researches. Gonzalez-Pola et al. (2005) studied an early spring pulse of downwelling observed in the western Cantabrian

shelf-slope; Alvarez et al. (2009) analyzed the evidence of a winter upwelling event in the northern Rias. The upwelled seawater inside the estuaries has a shelf bottom origin and it is not associated with Eastern North Atlantic Central Water or the Iberian Poleward Current as observed in the Western Rias (deCastro et al., 2006; Prego et al., 2007; deCastro et al., 2008); Alvarez et al. (2010) analyzed summer upwelling frequency along the Cantabrian Coast from 1967 to 2007 and monitored sea temperature related to wind forcing in the Barqueiro Ria.

The hydrographical, biogeochemical, plankton pattern and frequency of summer upwelling events for the Northern Rias remains still unknown. Moreover, downwelling episodes have not been described, such as in the Western Rias (deCastro et al., 2004; Torres and Barton, 2007). These episodes could be associated with red tides episodes (Fraga et al., 1988; Prego, 1992; Tilstone et al., 1994) that were not yet reported for the Northern Rias.

According to the wind patterns and coastal orientation, it may be hypothesised that the upwelling events in the Northern Rias and neighbouring shelf must be different to that of the rest of Galician rias. In this way, physical, chemical and biological, data were obtained in favourable and unfavourable upwelling conditions in July-August 2008. Therefore, the aims of this article are: (i) to characterize a summer both, upwelling and downwelling events in the Northern Galician Rias; (ii) to analyze the frequency of meteorological conditions favourable to upwelling and downwelling events in the northern coast of Galicia; (iii) to compare the oceanographic patterns of the current Northern Rias case with the existing information about the Middle and Western Rias.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

The northernmost point of the Iberian Peninsula, Cape Estaca de Bares (43°47.5'N), is located in the western coast of the Cantabrian Sea. In this area, there are three Galician Rias (Figure 1): Ortigueira (38 km² of surface), Barqueiro (10 km²) and Viveiro (27 km²). They form a whole named as 'Northern Galician Rias' or 'Rias Altas', according to the tectonic classification proposed by Torre Enciso (1958). This ria classification is also in accordance with the own hydrological pattern of the rivers running into the Northern Rias. At the innermost area, these Rias receive the fluvial discharges of the Mera, Sor and Landro Rivers (annual average flows of 4.2, 6.0 and 7.1 m³·s⁻¹, respectively; Río-Barja and Rodríguez-Lestegás, 1992). These flows are low compared with the fluvial contributions in the Western Galician Rias (Muros, Arosa, Pontevedra and Vigo) where the annual average river discharge ranges from 17 to 79 m³·s⁻¹. Therefore, marine processes mainly control the hydrodynamics of the Northern Rias, except at the innermost estuarine zone (mesotidal: tidal range of 2-4 m), which is partially enclosed with well-developed beach barriers (Lorenzo et al., 2007). For this reason the Northern Rias can be considered as funnel-like incised valleys characteristic of a relatively submerged coastline (Evans and Prego, 2003) with 30-35 m depth at their open mouths to the north swell. In this geographical area, climate is wet temperate oceanic (Cfb Köppen type), with an annual average of temperature of 13.1°C, ranging from 8°C in winter to 18°C in summer, and 1370 mm of precipitation with 130 days of rain per year.

2.2. Hydrographical and chemical water column sampling

Two cruises were conducted on board the RV *Mytilus* and RV *Lura* to investigate the oceanographic characteristics in the water column of the Northern Galician Rias during an upwelling and downwelling processes. The first cruise was carried out on July 16-17th after one week of upwelling favouring prevailing winds, and the second on August 19-20th during the upwelling relaxation phase, which started on 23rd July and dominated by western winds. Eighteen seawater stations were visited in the Rias of Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro (Figure 1). Six stations at different depths, between 10 and 100 m, were studied in every ria during July and seven stations during August. Vertical profiles of temperature and salinity were measured with a Seabird-9/11plus CTD placed in a SeaBird-32 Rosette (RV *Mytilus*) and a CTD SeaBird-25 with PAR and Fluorescence sensors placed in a General Oceanic Mini-Rosette (RV *Lura*). Water samples at each station were collected at standard depths (0, 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 90 m) using General Oceanic Niskin bottles of 5-L (RV *Lura*) or 12-L (RV *Mytilus*), for chemical and biological sub-sampling. Dissolved oxygen concentrations were measured at the next sampling day by Winkler titration of samples to calculate saturation percentages (Aminot, 1983). Nutrient salts were frozen onboard at -20°C and later analyzed in the laboratory using an Integral Futura autoanalyzer system (Alliance Instruments) with separate lines to nitrate, nitrite, ammonium, phosphate and silicate according to standard colorimetric methods (Hansen and Koroleff, 1999). Samples for analysis of chlorophyll-*a* were immediately filtered through a Whatman GF/F filter (25 mm diameter) and chlorophyll concentration was determinate by spectrofluorimetry (Neveux and Panouse, 1987) after extraction with 90% acetone according to the method described by UNESCO (1994).

2.3. Biological water column sampling

Particulate organic carbon and nitrogen (POC and PON, respectively) and plankton abundances of different groups were measured at station 5 (20 m depth) located in the middle of the channel of the Barqueiro Ria. To determine POC and PON water aliquots were filtered through glass microfiber filters (Whatman GF/F, 25 mm diameter) using a FlashEA 11-12 Termoquesth CNH analyzer; in the case of POC, carbonate was not removed from the filters, as the contribution of carbonate to total carbon represents only up to 2% of total particulate carbon (Fernández et al., 1995, Palanques et al., 2002). Samples for quantification of phytoplankton were preserved in Lugol's solution to be examined under a Nikon Eclipse TE 300 inverted microscope, following the technique described by Utermöhl (1958). The used nomenclature was based on Tomas (1997).

Planktonic ciliates were sampled and identified using a protocol similar to the one described for phytoplankton. Samples were sedimented during 48 hours in 100 ml chambers. Taxonomic classification was based on Lynn and Small (2002) criteria. The counting of individuals was performed at 200x magnification.

Samples of microzooplankton (40-200 µm) were collected with vertical hauls, of a 20 cm diameter bongo-type net of 40 µm mesh size, and filtering cod-ends was used. Samples were screened through 40 µm nylon mesh and fixed in 2% borate-buffered formalin before microscope examination. Taxonomic classification of species was based on Valdés et al. (1991) criteria.

1 Mesozooplankton samples were collected by oblique hauls a Juday-Bogorov net
2 with 200 μm mesh size (50 cm diameter) and equipped with flow and depth meters
3 (Bode et al. 1998). Samples were fixed in 4% formalin before microscope analysis.

4 **2.4. Hydrological and hydrochemical sampling of rivers**

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7 Daily river flow data of the main rivers running into the three Northern Rias during
8 July and August were supplied by the 'Aguas de Galicia' company dependent on
9 the 'Consellería de Medio Ambiente' of the 'Xunta de Galicia'. The flows were area
10 corrected considering the whole river basin area: 270, 202 and 127 km^2 of Landro,
11 Sor and Mera Rivers, respectively. These three rivers were sampled four times
12 near their mouth: 2nd, 15th and 30th July and 18th August. Salinity was verified using
13 a WTW MultiLine F/Set-3 (error range: ± 0.1). Dissolved oxygen concentrations
14 were measured at the next sampling day by Winkler titration of samples to
15 calculate saturation percentages (Aminot, 1983), with an error range of ± 0.2 .
16 Nutrient salts samples (nitrate, nitrite, ammonium and phosphate) were collected
17 in 50 mL plastic bottles and immediately frozen at -20°C ; then they follow the
18 previously cited procedure used for the seawater nutrient samples. As orthosilicate
19 polymerization may occur in freshwater frozen samples (Kobayashi, 1966), rivers
20 were also sampled using 10 mL plastic bottles and preserved at 4°C and dissolved
21 silicate was analyzed next day. The accuracy of the analytical procedure was
22 assessed by the analysis of certified reference materials: MOOS-1 (seawater
23 nutrients; NRC, Canada), obtaining good agreement with the certified values. The
24 precision as relative standard deviation (RSD) was always less than 5%. Samples
25 for chlorophyll-*a* analysis were also taken and processed as the seawater
26 samples.
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34 **2.5. Satellite and Meteorological data**

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36 Maps of Sea Surface Temperature (SST) have been elaborated using the
37 NASA GHRSSST satellite data base that combines measurements of several
38 thermal infrared (AVHRR, MODIS, AATSR and SEVIRI) and microwave (AMSR-E
39 and TMI) satellite sensors. The data set has a precision of 0.1K, a spatial
40 resolution of 5 km and a daily temporal resolution. Details of the processing at
41 NASA-JPL can be found at
42 ftp://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/GHRSSST/doc/GHRSSST_guide_doc.pdf.
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45 Surface wind fields from July to August 2008 were provided by the
46 QuikSCAT satellite, and retrieved from the Jet Propulsion Laboratory web site
47 (http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/quikscat/qscat_data.html). The data set consists of
48 global grid values of meridional and zonal components of wind measured twice
49 daily on an approximately $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid with global coverage. QuikSCAT data
50 are given in an ascending and descending pass. Data corresponding to one pass
51 present numerous shadow areas, therefore, an average between both passes was
52 considered to increase the coverage. It is necessary to take into account that wind
53 data close to coast (~ 25 km) are not available due to the existence of a small
54 coast mask, nevertheless, a statistical comparison between QuikSCAT wind
55 measurements and high resolution numerical models was carried out along the
56 Galician coast (Penabad et al., 2008), revealing similar results between models
57 and satellite data. Ekman transport was calculated using the wind speed from the
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1 QuikSCAT satellite at 5 control points located along the northern Galician coast at
2 latitude 44.25°N and from 8.25°W to 7.25°W (Figure 1).

3 Ekman transport data provided by the Pacific Fisheries Environmental
4 Laboratory (PFEL) (<http://www.pfeg.noaa.gov>) were considered from 1990 to
5 2008. The PFEL distributes environmental index products and time series data
6 bases to cooperating researchers, taking advantage of its long association with the
7 U.S. Navy's Fleet Numerical Meteorology and Oceanography Centre (FNMOC).
8 For our purposes six-hourly Ekman transport data model derived from Sea Level
9 Pressure were considered at a control point located at 43.5° N, 10.5° W (Figure 1,
10 gray square). Data were averaged to obtain daily series. Considering that UI can
11 be defined as the Ekman transport component in the direction perpendicular to the
12 shore-line (Nykjaer and Van Camp, 1994; Gomez-Gesteira et al. 2006), then the
13 Q_y component of the Ekman transport can be considered as the UI for the
14 Northern Galician Rias ($UI_N=+Q_y$). Positive values of UI ($\text{km}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) indicate
15 upwelling-favourable conditions. Conversely, negative values indicate
16 downwelling-favourable onshore Ekman transport. Along the western coast of the
17 Iberian Peninsula (Western Rias), the northerly component of shelf wind-stress
18 causes upwelling favourable conditions ($UI_W=-Q_x$) with offshore Ekman transport
19 (Wooster et al., 1976; Bakun and Nelson, 1991) and southerly winds result in the
20 opposite effect.
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25 **3. RESULTS**

26 **3.1. Meteorological situation and seawater transport**

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30 Images of SST along the Northern Galician Rias each five days between July
31 12 and August 19 of 2008 are presented in Figure 2. This figure also shows the
32 Ekman transport. At the beginning of July (days 8-12; Figure 2a) transport was
33 mainly directed southeastward, i.e. upwelling unfavorable according to the
34 coastline direction. Then, for the days previous to the cruise carried out in July
35 (days 13-17, Figure 2b), the transport pattern varied; it was completely different
36 pointing northwestward (upwelling favorable) along the coast and showing
37 approximately the same direction and amplitude at each point. This situation
38 remained during the very next days, (from July 18 to 22, Figure 2c), but the
39 transport pattern changed again at the end of the month (days 23-27, Figure 2d)
40 toward southeastward direction although with low intensity. This upwelling
41 unfavorable behavior persisted (Figure 2e) and increased in August; transport was
42 mainly directed southward (days 1-19, Figure 2f) showing the same direction and
43 amplitude at each point resulting in downwelling favorable conditions.
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48 **3.2. July Upwelling event**

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51 The TS diagram of thermohaline data (Fig. 3) measured inshore (st.5, Fig.1)
52 and offshore (st.8) of the three Rias under upwelling (July 17th, 2008) and
53 downwelling (August 19th, 2008) conditions (Fig. 2) shows the presence of a saltier
54 and colder water mass associated with the ENACW during the favourable
55 upwelling event of July. During July the main variables measured in the rivers are
56 shown in Table 1. The flow of rivers ranged from 0.4 to 7.5 $\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and temperature
57 and dissolved oxygen saturation from 16.1 to 19.7°C and from 96 to 98%,
58 respectively. Concentration levels of nutrient salts were in the range of 32-50 μM
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1 for nitrate, 0.1-0.2 μM for nitrite, 0.2-4.0 μM for ammonium, 0.1-2.9 μM for
2 phosphate and 99-215 μM for silicate while the values for Chlorophyll-*a* ranged
3 between 0.4-0.9 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Sor River is quasi-pristine.

4 In the rias and their neighbouring shelf, nutrient salts concentrations (Fig.4a
5 and 4b) increased with depth, reaching their maximum concentrations near bed.
6 Nitrate was practically depleted in the inner surface waters of Barqueiro and
7 Viveiro Rias and the highest values were measured at bottom near the shelfbreak
8 (in both rias: 9.2-9.5 μM nitrate). Ortigueira Ria presented a similar distribution
9 pattern but without nutrient depletion, with values from 1 to 13 μM nitrate as result
10 of upwelling inputs and remineralisation processes in the shelf seawater column
11 reflected by the high ammonium concentrations at mid seawater layers (up to 4.6
12 μM , Fig.4b). Phosphate (0.0-0.6 μM) and silicate (0.7-5.1 μM) showed similar
13 trends to those of nitrate in the three rias, however the highest concentrations
14 were at the top of the innermost ria stations (1.9 μM of phosphate in Ortigueira Ria
15 and 7.9 μM of silicate in Barqueiro Ria). Dissolved oxygen was only measured in
16 the Barqueiro Ria and showed a clear horizontal stratification (Fig.4a), with well-
17 oxygenated surface waters at surface (102%) and decreased oxygen saturation at
18 the bottom (72%).

19 Chlorophyll-*a* was low (0.1 to 0.7 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) in the Barqueiro and Viveiro Rias,
20 however an important increase up to 2.7 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ was observed in the Ortigueira Ria
21 at st.6 and 7 with the highest concentration in the first 20 m (Fig.4a and 4b).
22 Plankton abundances were quantified at st.5 in the Barqueiro Ria (Fig.1). The
23 mean abundances of phytoplankton (mean of four depths sampled; Table 2, July)
24 were dominated by naked flagellates with mean abundances of 500 cells·mL⁻¹.
25 Larger phytoplankton showed a predominance of diatoms, with 42 cells cells·mL⁻¹.
26 Auxospores of *Chaetoceros*, *Pseudo-nitzschia delicatissima*, *Guinardia delicatula*,
27 *Leptocylindrus minimus* and *L. mediterraneus* were the dominant species.
28 Dinoflagellates were less abundant than diatoms (abundances of 11 cells·mL⁻¹).
29 *Amphidinium flagellans*, *Prorocentrum minimum*, *Heterocapsa niei* and small
30 species of *Gymnodinium* were the dominant taxa in July. Other groups displayed
31 negligible abundances. Planktonic ciliates showed very low abundances, around
32 0.15 cells·mL⁻¹. *Lohmaniella oviformis* and *Strombidium acutum* were the dominant
33 taxa (Table 2, July). Microzooplankton abundance in July was high, around 12000
34 indiv·m⁻³, and dominated by larvae of copepods (nauplii), bivalves and gastropods.
35 Mesozooplankton abundance was also high with values above 5000 indiv·m⁻³, with
36 copepods (mainly copepodits), and appendicularia as the dominant groups (Table
37 3, July).
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46 **3.3. August Downwelling event**

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48 Temperature and salinity on 19th August 2008 at st.5 and 7 situated inside rias
49 and in their neighbouring shelf respectively, displayed a little variability; they varied
50 from 35.4 and 19.6°C near surface to 35.7 and 18.6°C near bed. The TS diagram
51 showed a clear difference respect to the upwelling situation of July (Fig.3). Under
52 these environmental conditions a depletion of nutrient salts was observed along
53 the water column of the Barqueiro Ria (Fig.4a) and offshore seawaters. Maximum
54 concentrations of nutrients were low close to the bottom: 1.4 μM of nitrate, 0.16
55 μM of nitrite, 1.4 μM of ammonium, 0.15 μM of phosphate (at surface in the
56 innermost ria station) and 3.5 μM of silicate. The main nutrient source to this old-
57 poor seawater was the fluvial outputs. The Sor River on 18th August 2008 (Table
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1) contributed to the Barqueiro Ria with $0.25 \text{ molN}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (96% as nitrate), $0.14 \text{ mmolP}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, $0.64 \text{ molSi}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, which was used by phytoplankton in the innermost ria zone where the highest concentration of chlorophyll-*a* was measured ($2.40 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$). There was a slightly increase of POC and PON concentration inside the Barqueiro Ria from July to August (St.5, from $920 \text{ mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and $175 \text{ mgN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ to $1370 \text{ mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and $210 \text{ mgN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$), similarly to C:N (mol:mol) ratio gone from 6.2 to 7.4.

Mean abundances of phytoplankton measured in August throughout the water column (Table 2) revealed that small flagellates were, as in July, the most abundant component of phytoplankton, with abundances higher than $1000 \text{ cells}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. Phytoplankton species composition of larger phytoplankton showed a dominance of diatoms. *Chaetoceros* auxospores, *Rhizosolenia* and *Thalassiosira* species, displayed similar abundances as those of July, while *P. delicatissima*, *G. delicatula*, *L. minimus* and *L. mediterraneus* clearly decrease in August. Significant increase was observed for small *Navicula* species, *Navicula transitans*, *Nitzschia longissima* or *Paralia sulcata*. Dinoflagellates remained with a similar abundances, reaching around $10 \text{ cells}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. Dominant species in July, dropped their abundances in August, and the more salient peculiarity is the high increase of the red tide forming species *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (from 10% of total dinoflagellates in July to 76% in August, Table 2). In any case, low phytoplankton abundances were observed both, in July and August, in dinoflagellates and diatoms as well. Planktonic ciliates were slightly higher than in July, with abundances around $1 \text{ cells}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. The taxa present in July, increased their abundances and some other species appeared as dominant in this date. This is the case of *Myrionecta rubra* and *Tontonia gracillima* (Table 2), Microzooplankton abundance clearly decreased as compared to those of July, reaching around $6000 \text{ indiv}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, with copepods nauplii larva as dominants, followed by bivalve larvae and some species of tintinnids (Table 3, August). Mesozooplankton also decreased with mean abundances about $3000 \text{ indiv}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Dominance shared among different groups, with copepods displaying higher densities, followed by appendicularia, cladocerans and bivalves larvae (Table 3, August).

3.4. Wind-induced conditions in the Northern and Western coast of Galicia

The upwelling phenomenon occurring in the areas close to northern and western coasts of Galicia can be compared from results shown in the Figure 5. In this figure, values of daily upwelling index during the upwelling seasons from 1990 to 2008 calculated at the 43.5°N - 10.5°W point were represented on an U_{W} versus U_{N} axes system. The northerly component of shelf wind-stress causes upwelling favourable conditions in the Western Galician coast ($U_{\text{W}}=-Q_x$) while the same occurs with the easterly component to the Northern coast. The figure corresponds to UI favourable in both coasts (positive U_{W} and U_{N}). UI points situated inside the figure fit to the lineal regression $U_{\text{N}}/U_{\text{W}}=0.94$ indicating that the upwelling conditions were 6% higher in the western shelf.

4. DISCUSSION

The Ekman transport sequence in the western Cantabrian Sea (Fig.2), resulting from the wind pattern triggered the high pressures crossing on Galicia (Wooster et al., 1976; Fiuza et al., 1982; Torres and Barton, 2007; Alvarez et al.,

2008), suggests that the observed upwelling and downwelling events may be as usual in the northern Galician coast as in the Western Rias area during the upwelling season (Prego, 1992; Tilstone et al., 1994; Diz et al., 2006).

During the upwelling event, ENACW was detected on the shelf off the Northern Rias (from 65 m depth to the bottom, Fig.3). Upwelling did not reach the surface water, where high temperatures were observed, especially at the inshore stations. Both facts seems to be usual resulting a significant difference with respect to the rias located close (Varela et al., 2005) and south (Rosón et al., 1997; Prego et al., 2001) Cape Finisterre because upwelling penetrates inside them, raising up to surface layers (Alvarez-Salgado et al 1993; Alvarez et al., 2005a). Another difference is the origin of the upwelled water mass. Western of Cantabrian Sea is characterized by the presence of ENACW from sub-polar origin (ENACW_P) (Fraga, 1981; Llope et al., 2006) while in the event of July 2008 (Fig.3), the subtropical branch (ENACW_T), formed along a front near the Azores (Fiuza et al., 1983; Rios et al., 1992), upwelled in the northern Galician coast, as it occurs in the Finisterre upwelling in the western coast (Blanton et al., 1984).

After the spring bloom of phytoplankton in the Western Rias the ENACW_T transport nutrient salts to the photic layer (Fraga 1981, Prego et al., 1999b) during the upwelling events turning these rias into eutrophic zones (Varela et al., 2008). This was not observed in the Northern Rias where low nitrate and chlorophyll concentrations were measured in the water column (Fig.4A). This highlights that upwelling did not affect these rias and they could be considered as mesotrophic systems. The innermost or estuarine ria zone may be an exception, even though this matter deserves more attention. However, the whole northern shelf was not evenly affected by the wind-induced upwelling. The Ortigueira zone was the most influenced with a significant vertical mixing in the lower layer of the water column, as shown by the TS diagram (Fig.3). The consequence is a higher input of nutrient salts to the photic layer, a subsequent phytoplankton growth and a remineralisation area marked both, by chlorophyll and ammonium maxima (Fig.4B). Nevertheless, this process occurs out the Ortigueira Ria but near its mouth. The Ortigueira case as compared to Barqueiro and Viveiro shelves could be only a consequence of the Cape Estaca de Bares effect because upwelling processes are more intense and persistent at southern areas of the capes (Crepon et al. 1984), as it was observed in the neighbouring Cape Peñas (Molina, 1972; Botas et al., 1990; Llope et al., 2006) and Cape Ajo (Lavín et al., 1998) in the central Cantabrian coast. On the other hand, in the Western Rias the remineralisation supplies recycled nutrients at the inner ria (Alvarez-Salgado et al., 1996; Prego, 2002), while in the Northern Rias this process is negligible.

During the downwelling event temperatures higher than those of upwelling were observed in the Northern Rias (Fig.3). Western winds moved the surface seawater coastward as indicated by the Ekman transport (Fig.2), a process similar to those observed in other Galician Rias (Cabanas and Alvarez, 2005). Waters were retained inside the rias, and nutrients were almost exhausted (Fig.4A). In these circumstances, river outflow might be the main nutrient source and consequently phytoplankton is constrained to the innermost ria zone as shown by the chlorophyll-*a* distribution. (Fig.4A). This can also explain the slightly increase of POC and PON concentration inside the Barqueiro Ria from July to August associated to a higher C:N ratio as a consequence of an enhanced remineralisation related to downwelling. However, remineralisation in the Northern Rias was not as important as in Western Rias where high concentrations of

recycled nutrients maintain a high biological activity (Alvarez-Salgado et al., 1996; Varela et al., 2004). In any case, low phytoplankton abundances were observed both, in July and August, although the enrichment of the water due to the upwelling may be reflected in an increase in the biomass of some species of phytoplankton and zooplankton (Tables 2 and 3), e.g *Pseudo-nitzschia* cf. *delicatissim* which abundance is associated with nitrate and nitrite concentrations (Kaczmarek et al. 2007, Loureiro, 2009). Other species of diatoms can be dominant in any season when silicate concentrations in water are greater than 2 μM (Egge and Aksnes 1992); this would explain why there are no great differences between the mean abundance of diatoms during July and August.

In the case under study at the northern shelf, there were nine days of upwelling favourable conditions previous to sampling, with average UI of $1095 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$. It occurred only ten times during the interval of 1990-2008. The poor intensity of upwelling events for the western Cantabrian coast was reported by Alvarez et al. (2010) who estimated a probability of around 17% for upwelling favourable conditions of at least five days from June to September. The downwelling occurred in northern region after seven days with an average UI of $-660 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$. The events in the Northern coast can be characterized by defining conditions to favourable upwelling (+UI_N) and downwelling (-UI_N) periods: at least one week with averages out of the range of $\pm 500 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$. Under these conditions, the average of upwelling events per year was 1.9 ± 0.8 from May to September during the studied period of nineteen years with an average of 12 ± 4 days of easterly winds and UI of $870 \pm 270 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$. Nevertheless, in 1997 not events were observed. The wind-forcing pattern in the Northern coast of Galicia is 6% less favourable to upwelling (75% of events) than in the Western zone (Fig.5). The difference between the two Galician regions increases when the lasting and intensity of the upwelling process are considered. UI values (up to $1390 \pm 180 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$; Alvarez et al., 2005a) and event time scale (10-15 days; Nogueira et al., 1997) are higher in the western shelf.

The frequency of downwelling was $2.1 \pm 1.0 \text{ event} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ (13 ± 7 days of westerly winds and $760 \pm 200 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$) with no cases in 1990, four in 1999 and three events higher than $-1000 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{km}^{-1}$ in the whole period. From May to September, downwelling was like upwelling—events in frequency. Downwelling was lower in intensity but they can last larger than upwelling. There were only six chained upwelling-downwelling transitions, including the one studied, during the period 1990-2008. This scarcity in upwelling-relaxations processes could explain why, red tides events were not yet reported for the Northern Rias while they are a typical event during downwelling in the Western Rias (Figueiras et al., 1994). In any case, the August downwelling was associated to a small red tide of *Lingulodinium polyedrum* which dominated the dinoflagellates community (Table 2).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The classical topics related to oceanographic patterns of Galician Rias are mainly derived from the initial studies carried out about upwelling and downwelling in the Western Rias. However, these topics need to be revised after the first results obtained in the Northern Galician Rias. In this northern coastline under wind induced upwelling conditions during summer, the upwelling remained out of rias affecting only the neighbouring shelf such as Prego and Bao (1997) forecasted. Therefore, in that time period Northern Rias tend to be mesotrophic

1 systems as indicated by nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations as well as
2 plankton abundances. On the contrary, under the same conditions, the Western
3 Rias tend towards eutrophy. A different shoreline direction seems to play a
4 significant role in the hydrographical, biogeochemical and biological patterns
5 during upwelling and downwelling events. More research should be undertaken
6 at the boundaries of the upwelling systems, such as that in northern Galicia (43°N)
7 respect to the eastern boundary of the central North Atlantic upwelling system
8 (43°-10°N).
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10 On the other hand, there are explicit geologic-tectonic (Torre-Enciso, 1958)
11 and implicit climatological-hydrological reasons (Soto and Díaz-Fierros, 1996)
12 to classify the Galician Rias in three categories: Northern, Middle and Western Rias.
13 The present study carried out in the Northern Rias, gives oceanographical reasons
14 to validate the above mentioned classification.
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Figure legends

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Figure 1. Map of Northern Galician Rias showing the sampling stations (black circles) of cruises carried out in July and August 2008. Asterisks in the upper-right map represent the five control points considered to analyze wind data provided by the QuikSCAT satellite. Gray square on the map in the right corner correspond to the control point (43.5°N, 10.5°W) for Ekman transport data considered from 1990 to 2008.

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) maps and Ekman transport pattern (white arrows) along the northern Galician coast during the upwelling-downwelling event. SST images correspond to the date shown on the lower-left corner of each frame. Ekman transport was calculated averaging the surface wind fields from QuikSCAT satellite data to the SST date and three previous days (lower-right corner of each frame).

Figure 3. TS diagram corresponding to the stations located at the mouth (St. 5) and at the continental shelf (July: St.8 and August: St.7) of the Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro Rias (see Fig.1). Grey band in the lower-right corner corresponds to the Eastern North Atlantic Central Water mass (ENACW).

Figure 4. Contour maps of nitrate, nitrite, ammonium and chlorophyll-*a* concentrations and dissolved oxygen saturation percentages along the main channel (sections in Fig.1) on July 17 for the three Northern Rias (A and B) and on August 19 to the Barqueiro Ria (A).

Figure 5. Daily upwelling index (UI) for the Northern Galician coast (UI_N) vs. the Western Galician coast (UI_W) calculated at the control point 43.5°N, 10.5°W. Data belong to the upwelling season (May-September) over the period of 1990-2008. Positive values of UI_W and UI_N correspond with UI favourable conditions in both coasts. Straight line shows the linear fit (as $y=ax$, p -value <0.001). The percentage of total data considered is also indicated.

Table 1[Click here to download Table: Table_1.doc](#)

Table 1. Master variables of the three main rivers flowing into the headwaters of the Northern Galician Rias. The measurements were made fortnightly during the months of the sea cruises.

River	Parameter	Date				Unit
		2 July	15 July	30 July	18 August	
Mera	Upwelling Index	-962	1421	-813	-713	$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$
	Flow	1.49	1.19	0.40	0.71	$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
	Temperature	16.1	17.3	17.0	17.4	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Dissolved oxygen saturation	-	97.5	-	95.5	%
	Nitrate	49.8	46.9	49.4	57.8	μM
	Nitrite	0.15	0.24	0.17	0.33	μM
	Ammonium	0.52	1.01	0.21	0.45	μM
	Phosphate	0.19	0.16	0.15	0.02	μM
Sor	Silicate	198	204	215	197	μM
	Chlorophyll-a	-	0.62	-	0.55	$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
	Flow	7.27	7.52	6.56	6.79	$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
	Temperature	18.3	19.1	19.7	20.3	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Dissolved oxygen saturation	-	98.0	-	98.0	%
	Nitrate	38.1	32.2	39.3	35.3	μM
	Nitrite	0.12	0.23	0.14	0.22	μM
	Ammonium	0.33	0.58	0.22	1.18	μM
Landro	Phosphate	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.02	μM
	Silicate	101	99	107	94	μM
	Chlorophyll-a	-	0.41	-	0.45	$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$
	Flow	4.82	3.65	2.80	2.59	$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
	Temperature	16.2	17.3	16.1	18.8	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Dissolved oxygen saturation	-	96.6	-	94.9	%
	Nitrate	43.1	41.0	41.3	49.2	μM
	Nitrite	0.14	0.23	0.16	0.27	μM
Landro	Ammonium	0.28	4.00	0.57	1.42	μM
	Phosphate	0.16	2.91	0.17	0.11	μM
	Silicate	150	-	160	150	μM
	Chlorophyll-a	-	0.92	-	0.64	$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$

Table 2

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Table 2. Mean abundance of phytoplankton and ciliates at station 5 in the Ria of 'O Barqueiro' in July and August 2008.

PLANKTON GROUP	JULY	AUGUST
PHYTOPLANKTON (cels·mL ⁻¹)		
(a) Dinoflagellate		
<i>Amphidinium flagellans</i>	1.88	0.37
<i>Cochlodinium helix</i>	0.19	0.19
<i>Gymnodinium</i> spp. small	1.50	0.00
<i>Gyrodinium fusiforme</i>	0.21	0.00
<i>Heterocapsa niei</i>	1.51	0.19
<i>Karlodinium</i> cf. <i>micrum</i>	1.31	0.00
<i>Lingulodinium polyedrum</i>	0.11	7.68
<i>Prorocentrum minimum</i>	3.35	0.74
<i>Protoperidinium steinii</i>	0.05	0.24
Total dinoflagellate	11.12	10.14
(b) Diatoms		
Auxoosporas de <i>Chaetoceros</i> spp.	7.70	7.83
<i>Amphora</i> spp.	0.76	0.00
<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i>	0.19	0.37
<i>Chaetoceros</i> cf. <i>convolutus</i>	0.21	1.69
<i>Chaetoceros danicus</i>	0.19	0.37
<i>Chaetoceros decipiens</i>	0.37	0.00
<i>Chaetoceros gracilis</i>	0.37	0.76
<i>Cocconeis</i> spp.	0.37	0.94
<i>Grammatophora marina</i>	0.01	0.19
<i>Guinardia delicatula</i>	3.34	0.01
<i>Guinardia striata</i>	0.19	0.01
<i>Gyrosigma</i> spp.	0.56	0.56
<i>Leptocylindrus mediterraneus</i>	2.78	0.00
<i>Leptocylindrus minimus</i>	4.28	1.48
<i>Navicula distans</i>	0.20	0.05
<i>Navicula</i> spp. small	0.37	5.57
<i>Navicula transitans</i>	0.74	2.60
<i>Nitzschia longissima</i>	1.52	4.82
<i>Paralia sulcata</i>	0.10	3.34
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> cf. <i>delicatissima</i>	8.30	0.74
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp.	1.11	2.41
<i>Proboscia alata</i>	0.19	0.20
<i>Rhizosolenia imbricata</i>	2.04	2.78
<i>Rhizosolenia setigera</i>	0.63	0.19
<i>Thalassiosira nana</i>	2.27	2.64
<i>Thalassiosira</i> spp.	2.41	2.23
Total diatoms	42.32	42.01
(c) Flagellates		
Flagellates 3-10 µm	532.14	1120.46
(d) PLANKTONIC CILIATES (cels·mL ⁻¹)		
<i>Lohmaniella oviformis</i>	0.05	0.27
<i>Myrionecta rubra</i>	0.00	0.31
<i>Tontonia gracillima</i>	0.00	0.19
<i>Strombidium acutum</i>	0.02	0.05
<i>Leegardiella sol</i>	0.01	0.05
<i>Srombidium epidemum</i>	0.00	0.04
<i>Strombidium</i> sp.	0.01	0.02
Total ciliates	0.14	1.07

Table 3

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Table 3.- Mean abundance of zooplankton at station 5 in the Ria of 'O Barqueiro' in July and August 2008.

PLANKTON GROUP	JULY	AUGUST
ZOOPLANKTON (individuals·m ⁻³)		
(e) Microzooplankton (40-200 µm)		
Copepods		
Nauplii larvae	7295	3415
Calanoids	68	49
Ciclopoids	545	212
Harpacticoids	34	0
Larvae		
Bivalves	2523	1536
Gasteropods	1023	392
Tintinnids		
<i>Eutintinnus</i> sp.	102	16
<i>Rhabdonella elegans</i>	102	654
<i>Favella</i> spp.	0	114
Other groups		
Apendicularia	136	49
Total microzooplankton	11898	6438
(f) Mesozooplankton (>200 µm)		
Apendicularia	749	501
Cladocerans		
<i>Evadne nordmanni</i>	7	8
<i>Evadne spinifera</i>	0	354
<i>Podon intermedius</i>	72	23
Copepods		
<i>Acartia clausi</i>	736	19
<i>Acartia juveniles</i>	768	60
<i>Calanus juveniles</i>	33	8
<i>Centropages chierchiae</i>	65	49
<i>Centropages juveniles</i>	788	45
<i>Clausocalanus</i> spp.	0	30
Copepodits	1902	320
<i>Ditrichocorycaeus anglicus</i>	0	11
<i>Euterpina acutifrons</i>	0	15
<i>Isias clavipes</i>	163	8
Nauplii larvae	39	11
<i>Oithona nana</i>	13	0
<i>Oithona similis</i>	169	222
<i>Oncaea media</i>	13	72
<i>Paracalanus parvus</i>	931	494
<i>Parapontella brevicornis</i>	26	0
Gastropods larvae	319	260
Crustacean larvae		
Braquiura zoea	20	4
Cirripods cypris	46	8
Cirripods nauplii	189	313
Decapods	26	4
Euphausacians	0	11
Bivalves larvae	46	369
Echinoderms larvae	0	23
Fish larvae	7	11
Sifonofora	0	19
Total copepods	5646	1364
Total mesozooplankton	7131	3289

Figure 1

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 5